

**THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR IMPROVING THE DURABILITY
OF FIXED JOINTS OF ROLLING BEARINGS RESTORED WITH
ANAEROBIC SEALANTS**

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Abstract. The article presents the results of experimental studies on the physical and mechanical properties of anaerobic sealants, determines the effect of curing temperature and fillers on destructive stresses, relative elongations and specific work at break.

Key words: bearing, anaerobic sealant, durability, curing, filler, technology, restoration, strength, specific work, stress.

Introduction. The restoration of rolling bearing seats using anaerobic adhesives is carried out by applying the adhesive to the mating parts, followed by assembling the joint and curing the adhesive. The durability of the resulting adhesive joint depends on its strength under static, dynamic, and cyclic loads. The strength of the adhesive joint is determined by both its adhesive and cohesive components. The adhesive and cohesive strengths must ensure the immobility of the bearing rings' connections with the housing and the shaft. The restored joints must be able to withstand torsional moments, axial, and bending loads without failure.

At present, there are several theories and perspectives that interpret the causes of adhesion differently. Well-known theories include the molecular (adsorption) theory, diffusion theory, chemical theory, micromechanical theory,

and others.

The molecular theory [1] studies the molecular interactions between the substrate and the adhesive, provided they have functional groups capable of interacting. According to this theory, the formation of an adhesive bond occurs in two stages. In the first stage, the molecules of the adhesive come into contact with the substrate surface due to the transport of adhesive molecules toward the substrate. In the second stage, intermolecular interaction begins once the adhesive molecules approach each other within a distance of 5 Å. This process continues until adsorption equilibrium is reached. According to the molecular theory, adhesion is influenced by all factors associated with the formation of the adhesive contact (such as the adhesive's ability to wet the substrate surface and spread over it, rheological phenomena, surface diffusion) and those that determine the completeness of the contact (such as the surface microrelief and cleanliness, adhesive viscosity, duration of the bonding process, and its conditions — pressure and temperature).

According to diffusion theory, adhesion arises as a result of mutual diffusion of polymers or other materials across the interface between phases. For diffusion processes to occur, mutual solubility and mobility of polymer macromolecules are required. Adhesion strength is influenced by the duration of diffusion, temperature, viscosity, molecular weights of the components, and other factors.

Based on chemical theory [1,2], in order to achieve a strong adhesive bond, the bonded materials must interact with each other to form covalent chemical bonds across the phase boundary.

The essence of the microrheological theory [3] lies in the fact that during the formation of the adhesive film, the adhesive fills the depressions of the rough substrate surface, which leads to an increase in the actual contact area and the number of bonds between the adhesive and the substrate.

One of the most important practical characteristics of an adhesive joint is its

adhesion strength.

Quantitatively, the adhesion strength of adhesive joints can be described by an equation [4].

$$A_o = \frac{Pt_k e^\alpha}{Ae^{U/RT_k}} K_1 V e^{U/RT_p} \quad (1)$$

where: where A_o is the adhesive strength of the bonded joint:

P – contact pressure;

t_k – contact duration;

α – viscosity parameter;

U – activation energy of viscous flow;

T_k – contact temperature;

V – rate of adhesive-substrate separation;

U_a – activation energy of adhesive failure;

T_p – separation temperature;

K_1 – coefficient accounting for the nature of the adhesive and substrate.

The adhesive strength of bonded joints depends on the viscosity parameter, which in turn is influenced by the degree of wetting, quantitatively determined by the contact angle.

Optimal wetting is achieved when the adhesive is applied in liquid form to a solid surface with a contact angle close to zero.

Contact temperature plays an important role in creating a strong adhesive bond [5]. The increase in joint strength with rising temperature is associated with a decrease in the adhesive's viscosity and more complete contact between the adhesive and the substrate. Furthermore, the rise in adhesive bond strength with increasing temperature may result from enhanced molecular mobility of the adhesive. However, excessive

temperature increase may reduce adhesive strength due to polymer degradation processes.

Thus, the analysis of various adhesion theories shows that adhesive joints with high adhesive strength can only be achieved when there is proper contact between the adhesive and the substrate. This contact should ideally be established over the maximum possible surface area. In the case of using liquid adhesives, maximum adhesive strength can be obtained when the surface roughness depressions are completely filled. To meet this requirement, it is necessary to ensure maximum cleanliness of the substrate surface during bonding. The adhesive must have excellent wetting ability towards the substrate, be able to spread over its surface, possess low viscosity, and effectively fill the surface roughness depressions. With an increase in bonding pressure, temperature, and time, the adhesive strength of the bonded joint increases.

The quantitative cohesive strength of the joint is determined by the formula [6].

$$f_M = \frac{\xi}{\beta} - \sigma_{\text{int}} \quad (2)$$

where: f_i – cohesive strength of the adhesive joint;
 ξ – molecular cohesion of the adhesive;
 β – stress concentration factor arising from the microscopic inhomogeneity of the solid body;
 σ_{int} – internal stresses that arise in the adhesive during its curing process.

The cured adhesive is bonded to the substrate surface through adhesive interaction, and therefore, during shrinkage phenomena, it becomes stretched compared to its equilibrium state. As a result, internal stresses are generated in the adhesive joint [6].

A formula has been proposed for determining the internal stresses in adhesive joints

$$\sigma_{\theta h} = \frac{E\varepsilon}{1-\mu} \quad (3)$$

where: E and μ are the modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio of the adhesive;

ε - shrinkage.

Internal stresses act against cohesive and adhesive forces.

Therefore, they can be equated to a long-term acting load. Internal stresses lead to the emergence of the energy required to detach the adhesive layer, which reduces the adhesive strength of the joint.

The internal energy of detachment can be determined using formula [6].

$$W_{\theta h} = \frac{\sigma_{\theta h}^2}{2E} S \cdot h, \quad (4)$$

where: $\sigma_{\theta h}$ – internal energy of separation;

S – the contact area of the adhesive with the substrate;

h – adhesive thickness.

By substituting equation (3) into equation (4), we obtain

$$W_{\theta h} = \frac{E\varepsilon^2}{2(1-\mu)^2} S \cdot h \quad (5)$$

Conclusion. Equation (5) shows that the internal energy of debonding increases with increasing shrinkage, elastic modulus, thickness, and area of the adhesive layer.

Therefore, to ensure high adhesive strength of the bonded joint, it is necessary to

select adhesives with low shrinkage and elastic modulus, as well as to limit the thickness of the adhesive layer.

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